

Human Reference Atlas

Style Guide

Human Reference Atlas Prose and Editorial Style Guide

For use with Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures

Authors: Elizabeth G. Record¹ and Todd N. Theriault¹

Approved by: Katy Börner¹ (May 1, 2026)

¹ Department of Intelligent Systems Engineering, Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering, Indiana University, Bloomington, IN 47408, USA.

Introduction

Style guides are valuable for maintaining a consistent voice and format, especially when many people are collaborating together on written products. This is an informal style guide for use when writing [Human Reference Atlas standard operating procedures](#).

The primary audience is those who are writing standard operating procedures for the Human Reference Atlas and those who are reviewing these documents for stylistic consistency. For stylistic guidance on typography, colors, logo use, and other aesthetic style choices, please see the [Human Reference Atlas Design Style Guide](#). For content advice see the [Human Reference Atlas Standard Operating Procedures Template](#).

Styles and Conventions

SOP titles

- SOP: is no longer included in the title of the SOP, either in the SOP itself or in the Zenodo community listing. This has changed and needs to be updated for SOPs published under previous versions. The Google document file name does retain SOP: in the title to facilitate sorting within the directory.
- Titles use title case.
- Subtitles should be limited to a single line, and use sentence case.

Affiliation

- Include the country name even when the country is USA. Do not use periods in USA.

Formatting the approval date

- In the SOP itself the approval date is formatted as Month DD, YYYY
- When entering Zenodo metadata, use YYYY/MM/DD

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Roles and Responsibilities

- Roles are listed in alphabetical order rather than in order of appearance or importance, both in the text and in the table.
- Use he or she, rather than singular they.
- Capitalize but do not bold the role names in the body of the text when the role is referenced in the procedural sections.
- Use various in lieu of name and email in the roles and responsibilities table when multiple people hold the role, or when who holds the role varies by project, organ, consortium, or team. Various is not a proper name or title so it should not be capitalized in the table.

Text

- Italics are used for level 3 and 4 headings and to denote a publication title in the reference section.
- Bold is only used in headings and to denote figures or captions.
- Underline is only used to indicate linked text.
- Links are underlined and light blue rather than the black of the main body text, in order to signify that they are links.
- Single quotes " are not used.
- Double quotes "" are only used to indicate a quotation or as called for in the references section.
- Parentheses () can be used for asides or clarifications, though commas are preferred. Em-dashes are also acceptable.
- Square brackets [] are used within quoted text, and are therefore not common in HRA standard operating procedures.
- Curly braces {} can be used in sections where code is displayed or where needed for mathematical formulae.
- Angle brackets or chevrons < > can be used to indicate placeholder text and may be needed when code is displayed.
- When code is represented in the procedures section, use a different font to indicate this.
 - Courier New (MS) is the recommended font.

Tables

See **Table 1**, below, for a sample table.

- Every table needs to have a descriptive caption.
- Use 10 point text for table captions.
- Use 10 point text for all text in the table.
- Captions are left aligned and not justified.

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- Captions are located above tables, with space between the caption and the table itself. This is accomplished by selecting Format, Line & paragraph spacing, and then adding space below the paragraph. This spacing is present in the template by default.
- Tables should be referenced from the body of the text.
- Bold the word **Table** and the table number when referring to a table in the main text.
- Bold text in the header row.
- Omit empty rows.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Data Providers	various	various

Figures

Fig. 1 is included as an example figure.

- All figures should be referred to from the main text. When figures are referred to in text they appear as **Fig. 1**, e.g., bold and with Fig capitalized.
- All figures need descriptive captions. **Figure** is bold in figure captions.
- Never use above or below to describe the location of the figure.
- Use at least 6 point text for all text in the figure to ensure legibility.
- Use 10 point text for figure captions.
- Captions are left aligned and not justified.
- Captions are located below figures, with space between the figure and caption. This is accomplished by selecting Format, Line & paragraph spacing, and then adding space above the paragraph. This spacing is present in the template by default.
- Include a 1 point dark gray box around screenshots or figures that have a white or light colored background. The SOP template is prepopulated with the correct border color and thickness.

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Figure 1. Overview of consortia contributing to the Human Reference Atlas and the organs they focus on.

Screenshots

Fig. 2 is included as an example of a screen shot incorporated into the text. Screenshots can be particularly useful for illustrating procedures that involve navigating software.

- All screenshots should be handled as figures and referred to from the main text.
- When capturing screenshots, use a high resolution so that images are legible in the SOP.
- Like all other figures, screenshots require a figure caption.
- Include an arrow, circle, or box to focus the reader's attention, if desired.

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Figure 2. Navigating to the HRA collection on the NIH BioArt website.

First person, second person, or third person

- Third person style is preferred.
 - Example: The Data Provider does x.
- An alternative can be to use an imperative sentence.
 - Example: Do x.
- Second person style is sometimes used in SOPs with a single actor, to avoid repetition.
 - Example: Next, you do x.
- Use active voice, where the subject of the sentence performs the action of the verb, in order to reduce ambiguity and increase clarity.

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Preferred Terms

- Use “constructing” rather than “building” when referring to the HRA.
- Use GitHub rather than Github or github or GH.
- More recent SOPs use 3D reference models rather than 3D reference organs. We no longer use the term reference organs because some of the models are not organs but anatomical structures.
- Dataset rather than data set.
- Do not include a final backslash in urls.
- Use a true em dash (—) rather than two hyphens (--).

Links to external resources

- When linking to published HRA SOPs, link to published persistent Zenodo links that resolve to the latest version automatically. Do not link to draft or unpublished SOPs.
- It is desirable to link to other SOPs to show how they fit into the HRA ecosystem.
 - Related SOPs are often mentioned in the introduction and in procedures that are adjacent but documented in other SOPs.
- Links are typically included as linked text, rather than as an unlinked URL, or a chip. Full URLs quickly get in the way of easy readability.
 - When the link is central to the procedure, include the full URL in the reference section, so users can find the link even if the URL becomes unlinked. This is usually included in the Zenodo citation automatically.
- When other SOPs are referenced in the body of the text, the titles are linked text.
- When referred to in the text, SOP titles are not italicized and titles are not in quotes.
- When scholarly publications are cited in the text of the SOP, use in text citations with the Chicago Manual of Style author-date format, rather than linked DOIs. When websites, document templates, folders, or SOPs are referenced, use linked text rather than in-text citation.
- Do not use anchor links to bookmarked locations within an SOP.
- When a number of resources such as GitHub prepositories, documents, or links are needed to perform procedures, consider grouping them in an optional Resources section that contains a table with titles, links, and descriptions of important resources. See the HRA SOP template for an example.

Appendices

- Link to the actual file or form or resource when the user needs to perform some action, such as when a form needs to be downloaded and filled out, or when pointing to information that is updated frequently and it is important to access the current version.

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- When the user needs to see fields in, for example, a survey or form, attach a PDF of the form as an appendix after the glossary. Appendices should be referenced from the main body of the SOP.

Capitalization

- Acronyms are presented with all letters capitalized, e.g. API.
- Use the all-capitals versions of file formats in text. For example,
 - XML, rather than .xml
 - GBL, rather than .gbl
 - SVG, rather than .svg
 - AI, rather than .ai
- Do not capitalize the following terms when used in the body of the text:
 - digital objects
 - 3D reference objects
 - functional tissue units
- Capitalize Human Reference Atlas when referring specifically to this human reference atlas.
- Capitalize the word portal in Human Reference Atlas Portal and HRA Portal.
- Capitalize the abbreviations for major HRA applications such as CDE, EUI, RUI.
- Use the proper mix of upper and lower case for HRApop, CTann, and HRAlit.
- Uberon should be capitalized since it is the proper name of an ontology. When referring to an Uberon ID, use UBERON, (e.g., UBERON:0000955 for brain).
- When referencing a command, UI menu item, or button name, capitalize the first letter of the name, but do not use any additional accentuation like quotation marks. [Microsoft's Help Text Guidelines](#) can provide suggestions and examples for best practices when describing interactions with software.

Abbreviations

- In titles, terms should be spelled out and abbreviations should not be used.
- Refrain from using abbreviations in the introduction and only introduce abbreviations in the main body of the SOP. Given that user research has shown that one of the leading barriers to adoption of the HRA is the use of specialized vocabulary and abbreviations, and given that SOPs are designed to be written in "plain English," the goal is to err toward the use of full terms rather than abbreviations whenever feasible.
- The first instance of any term should be spelled out in the body of each SOP, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses. The abbreviation should be used consistently thereafter.
- Some terms that are abbreviated when used frequently within the text of a particular SOP:

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- 3D rather than three-dimensional
- digital object (DO)
- functional tissue unit (FTU)
- anatomical structures (AS)
- cell types (CT)
- biomarkers (B) - only abbreviate this term within the context of ASCT+B.

References

- References are provided using the Chicago Manual of Style, 17th Edition style, in a list.
- In text citations are in the (author date) format.
- Indent rather than using bullet points to separate each reference.
- Italics are used for journal titles.
- When a paper includes more than six authors, the first six authors are listed, followed by et. al.
- Do not include a blank line between references.
- References are added in Zotero by a trained member of CNS, using the CNS Zotero account.
- Https is included in a publication's DOI, as per the Chicago Manual of Style.

Glossary

- Terms are listed alphabetically rather than in the order they appear in the text.
- When available, use definitions from the [SOP Glossary](#). If you need to define a term that does not yet exist in the master glossary, draft a definition. New or revised definitions must be reviewed before they are added to the master glossary.
- Terms are not capitalized in the glossary unless they are proper names.